

Synthesis and characterization of polyhalogen copper phthalocyanine

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Abstract : Polyhalogen copper phthalocyanine has been synthesized by bromination with liquid bromine and chlorine gas at 156–158 °C under acidic melt media, made with eutectic mixture of aluminium chloride and sodium chloride, followed by chlorination at 156–158 °C. The resultant halogenated mass isolated by pouring it into the mixture of water and hydrochloric acid. The crude pigment thus obtained evaluated analytically in terms of degree of halogenation and number of atomic substitution.

Keywords : Polyhalogen, eutectic, Pigment Green 36.

Introduction

Pigments with condensed aromatic or heterocyclic ring systems are known as polycyclic pigments, which are classified as non-azo pigments. The several pigments classes that fall into this category reflect their commercial importance¹. Phthalocyanine pigments, from the phthalocyanine structure, a tetraazotetrabenzoporphine, which belongs to the aza-(18)-annulene family, an aromatic macrocyclic hetero-system with 18 π electrons, which form conjugated double bonds are polycyclic pigments. The word phthalocyanine is derived from Greek terms naphtha (rock oil) and for cyanine (dark blue)². Although this basic molecule can chelate with a large variety of metals under various coordination condition, today only copper(II) phthalocyanine are of practical importance as pigments. The molecule adopts a planar and completely conjugated structure which exhibits exceptional stability. The unit cell contains two centrosymmetric molecules. Excellent general chemical and physical properties, combined with good economy, make this pigment the largest fraction of organic pigments in the market today¹.

ICI introduced the first copper phthalocyanine blue to the market as early as 1935, followed by first phthalocyanine green prepared commercially in Germany 1938, and subsequently by US companies in 1940³⁻⁶. The products were first marketed in 1959^{7,8}. At present, phthalocyanine blue and green are among the most important organic pigments in the market and are sold in large volume.

The synthesis and characterization of polyhalogen copper phthalocyanine seems to be beneficial keeping in view the commercial importance of the pigment. Patents

and literature survey shows the synthesis of the title compound with different methods⁹⁻¹⁸. Polyhalogen copper phthalocyanine i.e. Pigment Green 36 (hereafter, P.G.36) C.I. No. 74265; CAS No. 14302-13-7; EINECS No. 238-238-4¹⁹ produces very yellowish shades green pigment.

The pigment yellower than Pigment Green 7 (hereafter, P.G.7), which is fully chlorinated copper phthalocyanine. The exact hue which is produced by a green copper phthalocyanine is defined only by the degree of halogenation and by the types of halogens used (chloro and bromo substitution) and not by crystal phases. Only one crystal modification of copper polyhalophthalocyanine has been reported²⁰. The color of P.G. 36 becomes yellower as more chlorine atoms are replaced by bromine atoms. In the USA, these products are therefore, classified according to the yellowness of the shade and the bromine content. The bromine content may range from 25–30 wt% for less yellowish to 50–53 wt% for considerably yellower varieties.

P.G. 36, halogen derivatives of neutral complex of tetrafunctional ligand with divalent copper ion provides excellent lightfastness^{21,22}, based on ASTM standard No.

Table 1. Synthetic aspects and degree (%) of substitution

Sl. no.	Process variables	% Bromine	% Chlorine
(A) Use of different composition :			
1.	Halogenation at 180 °C	32.92	24.87
2.	Halogenation at 180 °C, using Cu catalyst	52.6	10.6
3.	Halogenation at 158 °C, using Cu catalyst	53.85	10.0
4.	Halogenation at 158 °C, using Cu catalyst and excess (+20%) liq. bromine	60.6	5.9
5.	With reduced (-30%) qty. of AlCl ₃	50.89	11.79
6.	With reduced (-20%) qty. of AlCl ₃	51.11	13.25
7.	With reduced (-10%) qty. of AlCl ₃	52.52	10.51
8.	With reduced (+30%) qty. of AlCl ₃	50.01	13.93
9.	With reduced (+20%) qty. of AlCl ₃	54.0	10.94
10.	With reduced (+10%) qty. of AlCl ₃	58.75	7.48
11.	Replacing 30% AlCl ₃ with AlBr ₃	54.5	10.7
12.	Replacing 20% AlCl ₃ with AlBr ₃	49.73	14.04
13.	Replacing 10% AlCl ₃ with AlBr ₃	49.0	14.54
(B) Use of different blue derivatives :			
14.	Replacing 20% blue with monochloro CPC blue	47.3	15.51
15.	Replacing 10% blue with monochloro CPC blue	52.0	12.61
16.	Replacing 5% blue with monochloro CPC blue	54.99	10.01
(C) Use of different temperature :			
17.	With higher (200 °C) temperature	51.5	10.75
18.	With lower (120 °C) temperature	54.99	10.44
19.	With optimum (158 °C) temperature	58.5	7.89
(D) Use of different catalyst :			
CuBr-catalyst :			
20.	Using CuBr-catalyst	53.1	11.25
21.	Using + 2% CuBr-catalyst	53.09	11.67
22.	Using + 5% CuBr-catalyst	54.0	11.01
23.	Using + 10% CuBr-catalyst	51.99	9.9
CuI-catalyst :			
24.	Using CuI-catalyst	53.19	10.51
25.	Using + 2% CuI-catalyst	54.35	10.86
26.	Using + 5% CuI-catalyst	56.6	8.69
27.	Using + 10% CuI-catalyst	53.5	10.7
Cu-catalyst :			
28.	Using Cu-catalyst	59.9	6.75
29.	Using + 2% Cu-catalyst	58.75	7.69
30.	Using + 5% Cu-catalyst	57.7	8.3
31.	Using + 10% Cu-catalyst	54.35	10.93
CuCl ₂ -catalyst :			
32.	Using CuCl ₂ -catalyst	62.27	5.15
33.	Using + 2% CuCl ₂ -catalyst	62.0	5.3
34.	Using + 5% CuCl ₂ -catalyst	60.0	6.7
35.	Using + 10% CuCl ₂ -catalyst	60.5	6.37
(E) Use of different combinaton of catalyst (Cu + CuCl₂) :			
36.	95 : 5 (Cu : CuCl ₂) wt%	61.97	5.38
37.	90 : 10 (Cu : CuCl ₂) wt%	61.2	5.93
38.	85 : 15 (Cu : CuCl ₂) wt%	58.9	7.54
39.	80 : 20 (Cu : CuCl ₂) wt%	58.0	8.14
40.	75 : 25 (Cu : CuCl ₂) wt%	55.7	9.91

Table-1 (contd.)

41.	70 : 30 (Cu : CuCl ₂) wt%	57.6	8.29
42.	65 : 35 (Cu : CuCl ₂) wt%	57.5	8.36
43.	60 : 40 (Cu : CuCl ₂) wt%	55.7	9.8
44.	55 : 45 (Cu : CuCl ₂) wt%	56.0	9.53
45.	50 : 50 (Cu : CuCl ₂) wt%	56.9	8.71
46.	45 : 55 (Cu : CuCl ₂) wt%	55.85	9.75
47.	40 : 60 (Cu : CuCl ₂) wt%	58.0	8.23
48.	35 : 65 (Cu : CuCl ₂) wt%	57.5	8.57
49.	30 : 70 (Cu : CuCl ₂) wt%	59.8	6.93
50.	25 : 75 (Cu : CuCl ₂) wt%	61.7	5.59
51.	100 (CuCl ₂) wt%	62.27	5.15
52.	100 (Cu) wt%	60.6	6.34

Table 2. Characterization – atomic substitution

Sl. no.	Process variables	Corresponding bromine atoms	Corresponding chlorine atoms	Total substitution	Non substitution
(A) Use of different composition :					
1.	Halogenation at 180 °C	5.48	9.33	14.81	1.19
2.	Halogenation at 180 °C, using Cu-catalyst	10.04	4.56	14.6	1.4
3.	Halogenation at 158 °C, using Cu-catalyst	10.46	4.38	14.84	1.16
4.	Halogenation at 158 °C, using Cu-catalyst and excess (+20%) liq. bromine	12.69	2.79	15.48	0.52
5.	With reduced (-30%) qty. of AlCl ₃	9.58	5.0	14.58	0.42
6.	With reduced (-20%) qty. of AlCl ₃	10.05	5.87	15.92	0.08
7.	With reduced (-10%) qty. of AlCl ₃	9.98	4.5	14.48	1.52
8.	With reduced (+30%) qty. of AlCl ₃	9.72	6.1	15.82	0.18
9.	With reduced (+20%) qty. of AlCl ₃	10.8	4.93	15.73	0.27
10.	With reduced (+10%) qty. of AlCl ₃	12.2	3.5	15.7	0.3
11.	Replacing 30% AlCl ₃ with AlBr ₃	10.98	4.86	15.84	0.16
12.	Replacing 20% AlCl ₃ with AlBr ₃	9.62	6.12	15.74	0.26
13.	Replacing 10% AlCl ₃ with AlBr ₃	9.42	6.3	15.72	0.28
(B) Use of different blue derivatives :					
14.	Replacing 20% blue with monochloro CPC blue	8.92	6.59	15.51	0.49
15.	Replacing 10% blue with monochloro CPC blue	10.3	5.63	15.93	0.07
16.	Replacing 5% blue with monochloro CPC blue	11.02	4.52	15.54	0.66
(C) Use of different temperature :					
17.	With higher (200 °C) temperature	9.59	4.51	14.1	1.9
18.	With lower (120 °C) temperature	11.15	4.77	15.92	0.08
19.	With optimum (158 °C) temperature	12.2	3.71	15.91	0.09
(D) Use of different catalyst :					
CuBr-catalyst :					
20.	Using CuBr-catalyst	10.45	4.99	15.44	0.56
21.	Using + 2% CuBr-catalyst	10.56	5.23	15.78	0.22
22.	Using + 5% CuBr-catalyst	10.82	4.97	15.79	0.21
23.	Using + 10% CuBr-catalyst	9.6	4.12	13.72	2.28
CuI-catalyst :					
24.	Using CuI-catalyst	10.29	4.58	14.87	1.13
25.	Using + 2% CuI-catalyst	10.95	4.93	15.88	0.12
26.	Using + 5% CuI-catalyst	11.44	3.96	15.4	0.6
27.	Using + 10% CuI-catalyst	10.49	4.73	15.22	0.78
Cu-catalyst :					
28.	Using Cu-catalyst	12.59	3.2	15.79	0.21
29.	Using + 2% Cu-catalyst	12.27	3.62	15.89	0.11
30.	Using + 5% Cu-catalyst	11.9	3.86	15.76	0.24
31.	Using + 10% Cu-catalyst	10.97	4.97	15.84	0.16

Table-2 (contd.)

Cu-Cl ₂ -catalyst :					
32.	Using CuCl ₂ -catalyst	13.4	2.5	15.9	0.1
33.	Using + 2% CuCl ₂ -catalyst	13.29	2.56	15.85	0.15
34.	Using + 5% CuCl ₂ -catalyst	12.63	3.18	15.81	0.19
35.	Using + 10% CuCl ₂ -catalyst	12.8	3.04	15.84	0.16
(E) Use of different combination of catalyst (Cu + CuCl ₂) :					
36.	95 : 5 (Cu : CuCl ₂) wt%	13.3	2.6	15.9	0.1
37.	90 : 10 (Cu : CuCl ₂) wt%	13.05	2.85	15.85	0.15
38.	85 : 15 (Cu : CuCl ₂) wt%	12.3	3.55	15.85	0.15
39.	80 : 20 (Cu : CuCl ₂) wt%	12.01	3.8	15.81	0.19
40.	75 : 25 (Cu : CuCl ₂) wt%	11.35	4.55	15.9	0.1
41.	70 : 30 (Cu : CuCl ₂) wt%	11.84	3.84	15.68	0.32
42.	65 : 35 (Cu : CuCl ₂) wt%	11.81	3.87	15.65	0.35
43.	60 : 40 (Cu : CuCl ₂) wt%	11.32	4.49	15.81	0.29
44.	55 : 45 (Cu : CuCl ₂) wt%	11.39	4.37	15.77	0.23
45.	50 : 50 (Cu : CuCl ₂) wt%	11.6	4.0	15.6	0.4
46.	45 : 55 (Cu : CuCl ₂) wt%	11.38	4.48	15.86	0.14
47.	40 : 60 (Cu : CuCl ₂) wt%	12.04	3.85	15.89	0.11
48.	35 : 65 (Cu : CuCl ₂) wt%	11.88	3.99	15.87	0.13
49.	30 : 70 (Cu : CuCl ₂) wt%	12.6	3.29	15.89	0.11
50.	25 : 75 (Cu : CuCl ₂) wt%	13.22	2.7	15.92	0.08
51.	100 (CuCl ₂) wt%	13.4	2.5	15.9	0.1
52.	100 (Cu) wt%	12.85	3.03	15.88	0.12

D 4303²³, weather fastness, heat stability and solvent fastness²⁴. This good to excellent fastness properties have attributed the pigment to gain commercial recognition P.G. 36 is not actually toxic. In the Ames test it is not mutagenic²⁵.

Experimental

Materials :

The chemicals, anhydrous aluminium chloride, sodium chloride, copper phthalocyanine blue, different copper salts, copper powder, liquid bromine, hydrochloric acid were of commercial grade and used as such. Blue derivative was used as received.

Pigment synthesis :

Preparation of melt from eutectic mixture :

Made a eutectic mixture of 30 parts of anhydrous aluminium chloride and 17 parts of sodium chloride. Heated together so called, mixture under dry condition, slowly upto 170 °C. Completely fluid melt observed.

Bromination :

Added at 156–158 °C, to the molten eutectic mixture, under stirring, a mixture of 54 parts of aluminium chloride, 11 parts of sodium chloride, 35 parts of copper phthalocyanine blue and 2.0 parts of copper powder in

15–20 min followed by slow addition of 107 parts of liquid bromine in about 22 h. Then passed dry gaseous chlorine at 156–158 °C into the mixture, under stirring. At first, effluent gases contain a little bromine. Completion of bromination reaction indicated, when no more inorganic bromine compounds remain in the reaction mixture. The operation is allowed to take about 18 h.

Chlorination :

Subsequent to bromination reaction, continued passage of gaseous chlorine into the reaction at 156–158 °C. Reappearance of bromine in the effluent gas is an indication that bromine which has entered the phthalocyanine nucleus is being replaced by chlorine i.e. completion of chlorination reaction. Passage of gaseous chlorine is then, stopped. This operation required about 3 h duration.

Isolation :

Hydrolyse the reaction mass by drowning resultant melt into the mixture of 1500 parts of water and 40 parts of hydrochloric acid (35% w/w). Stirred the green suspension for 30 min. Filtered, washed till neutral. The pigment was isolated. The isolated crude pigment, having 58–60 wt% bromine and 7–6 wt% chlorine can be subjected to different solvent crystallization process to get pigment with good pigmentary value.

Measurements :

Elemental analysis of the pigments were carried out, using decomposition method by sodium peroxide, wherein, pigments were subjected to decomposition by sodium peroxide in a bomb, followed by potentiometry titration of the resultant sodium halides with silver nitrate solution. The IR spectra (KBr pellets) of the title compound were scanned on FT-IR-therminicolate IR200 spectrophotometer. ESR spectra of the compound was scanned on Varian-E122 ESR spectrometer using 9.1 GHz (X-band) microwave range frequency.

Results and discussion

Elemental analysis :

The title pigment was prepared by applying different process parameters and crude pigments thus, obtained analytically evaluated by elemental analysis in terms of degree of halogenation and further, characterized in terms of atomic substitution.

Several data based on the degree of halogenation reported in Table 1.

Table 1, shows that, higher degree of bromination and hence, atomic substitution obtained with optimized quantity of composition and temperature. Since bromination through the said method depends on several important factors such as, ratio of components of eutectic mixture, effective use of bromine at optimum temperature, disturbance in composition and temperature yields lower degree of bromination. Use of copper phthalocyanine derivative at different dosage level, interrupts the feasibility of bromination of copper phthalocyanine which results into lower degree of bromination. Catalyst, by nature and dosage level, have influence on halogenation, Cu and CuCl₂, both have almost similar effect on degree of bromination. This has been further confirmed by the fact that, various combination ratio of catalyst (Cu + CuCl₂) gave pigment with bromination degree in the range of 55–60% wt.

On the basis of elemental analysis, substitution pattern for bromination, chlorination and hence, total substitution studied.

Table 2, describes the corresponding data on the basis of the substitution value.

It has been observed that under optimum process parameters such as temperature, proper eutectic mixture, described quantity of liquid bromine and nature and dosage of catalyst leads to higher atomic bromine (12.2–13.4) and corresponding chlorine (3.71–2.5) substitution, while

deviation in one of the said, results into variety, but lower atomic bromine (5.48–12.2) substitution and corresponding chlorine (9.33–3.5) atoms. As a result, structure of the compound based on of atomic substitution can be characterized as follows :

IR spectral study :

Fig. 1 shows spectra (KBr pellets), which helps to reveal the structure of the title compound. The observed characteristic wave numbers (cm⁻¹) are 447(m) and 531(m) for metal-N bond, 730–950 for aromatic ring with halogen derivatives, 1100(s) for the presence of C–N bond, 1300(s) for the presence of C=N bond.

Thus, the said spectral data further supports, the structure, which has been characterized based on atomic substitution.

Fig. 1 The IR spectra (KBr pellets) of the title compound.

ESR spectral study :

Fig. 2 shows X-band ESR spectra of the title compound. g_{\parallel} (g -parallel) = 2.12 and g_{\perp} (g -perpendicular) = 2.06. The spectral structure, g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} values well coincide with the known literature data^{26–28} of copper phthalocyanine, which confirms and supports square planar complex structure of the compound with the metal atom is effectively protected within the interior of the molecule.

Further, the absence of hyperfine structure could be attributed to the stronger valency of Cu electrons with two neighboring N atoms of porphine ring and also has co-ordinated linkage with two other nitrogens of the same ring²⁹. In the literature, there are some given expressions and comparisons that give much information about the magnetic copper ion, such as an expression related with anisotropic $g_{\parallel} = 2.12$ and $g_{\perp} = 2.06$ values (These g -values, respectively, denote the effective Lande splitting factors when the external DC field is parallel, B_{\parallel} and perpendicular, B_{\perp} to the symmetry axis of the crystalline field around the paramagnetic center), $G = (g_{\parallel} - 2)/(g_{\perp} - 2) = 2.0$ and when G is evaluated to be less than 4, supports the exchange interaction among Cu^{2+} ions as well³⁰. In addition, there is a general trend about the orbital energy levels for d electrons of copper (Cu^{2+}) ion that if $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > 2$ then this means unpaired magnetic electron locates mainly in $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital³¹. Further, the symmetrical nature of the structure has been supported by the excellent stability³² of the compound.

Fig. 2. X-Band ESR spectra of the title compound.

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